

ENGLISH TEACHERS SHIFTING CAREERS: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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English Teachers Shifting Careers: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study was to explore the stories and experiences of English teachers shifting careers. The study was conducted in Davao de Oro. A multiple case study was employed and purposive sampling was utilized in selecting the three participants. Moreover, the researcher adhered to the following criteria: (a) Who are willing to share their stories (b) Who graduated as BSED English major (c) Who are passers of LET (d) Who shifted careers. As part of the ethical consideration, the identities of the three participants were kept confidential and anonymous. The findings of the study revealed that the experiences encountered by the participants related to teaching were Worthwhile, Enjoyable, and Tricky and complicated. The challenges encountered by the participants related to teaching were Time management, and Catching students' Interest. The reasons of moving away from English teaching were Health Condition, Salary Wise, and to have stable job. The insights they developed were to Teaching the Noblest Profession, Finding it Necessary for Further Education, and Establish Understanding with Others.

Keywords: *English teachers shifting careers, experiences, challenges, reasons, insights, multiple case study*

Introduction

Transitioning from being an English teacher to a different career path presents many opportunities. By acquiring analytical, communicative, and critical thinking abilities by studying English, English teachers acquire the necessary tools to excel in diverse domains. They take pride in adaptability and distinctive skills as they begin a new chapter in their career paths. Frequent and unpredictable changes characterize the modern work environment. Consequently, position stability and predictability decrease while work changes' frequency and complexity rise (Masdonati, Fournier, & Lahrizi, 2017).

Changing careers does not only exist in the Philippines; Anderson (2009) reported in a paper titled A Study in Supply and Demand that Ohio English instructors saw an oversupply of English teachers as early as 1929. His research findings indicated that 35% of individuals with a major in English pursued a career as English teachers, while 7% were engaged in professions unrelated to teaching English. Furthermore, a significant majority (58%) did not pursue a career in teaching at all. Consequently, initial polls revealed that most of those majoring in English opted against pursuing professions in teaching. Fewer English majors will continue teaching if there is an oversupply of English teachers. At the same time, a more significant number will change careers because an English major is adaptable to other jobs.

On the other hand, in the Philippines, English major graduates perceive limited job prospects in teaching, particularly in the Philippines, where competition for teaching positions can be high (Rafael, 2016; Salcedo, 2019). English majors may explore diverse career paths beyond teaching, such as writing, editing, publishing, content creation, public relations, and corporate communications (Tiongco, 2017; Salcedo, 2019), and sometimes, they prioritize opportunities for professional growth which they believe that it is readily available in other careers instead of teaching English.

This circumstance led the researcher to undertake this study since some English major graduates from Davao de Oro are leaving their teaching careers. Thus, the study intends to conduct this study and investigate the stories and experiences of these English major graduates.

Research Questions

The research was geared to investigate the experiences, challenges, reasons, and the gained insights of three English teachers shifting careers in Davao De Oro. This study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of English teachers in teaching?
2. What are the challenges encountered by the English teachers in teaching?
3. What are the reasons that lead the English teachers shift careers?
4. What insights did the English teachers gain from their experiences?

Methodology

Research Design

The study followed a multiple case study methodology. The case study methodology is a research approach that involves conducting a thorough investigation of a particular bounded system. This strategy employed multiple data gathering strategies to methodically acquire information about the operations and functionalities of the system (Mills, Durepos, & Wiebe, 2010). This research sought to explore the stories and experiences of five English teachers shifting careers. Thus, a multiple case study approach was suited for this

research. To develop a comprehension of the matter, cases were carefully selected.

In a multiple case study, several examples are analyzed to gain insight into the similarities and distinctions among them, as well as to determine how particular cases may be impacted by various surroundings and the precise circumstances that lead to certain outcomes. Yin (2003) describes how multiple case studies can be used to either, (a) predicts similar results (a literal replication) or (b) predicts contrasting results but for predictable reasons (a theoretical replication).

Participants

Following the process of identifying qualified research subjects, the researcher interviewed five research informants who shifted careers from Davao De Oro. Participants were particularly chosen as they had personal experiences in shifting careers from being English teacher.

In addition, the researcher identified and selected the participants using of the following selection criteria: they must be (a) willing to share their stories, (b) BSED English majors, (c) LET passers (d) shifted careers.

Procedure

In order to achieve its purpose, this qualitative research work required thorough and methodological procedures. From the conceptualization stage to the gathering of all the data and until the end result of this research, the researcher participated in a series of events as Creswell (2007) stated that qualitative researchers engage in a sequence of tasks while gathering data. Before to proceed with the study, the researcher will obtain the endorsed referral letter from the graduate school. Then, the researcher had her research questionnaires validated.

To gather the information needed, a proper protocol and standard operating procedures was done through the following:

First, I ensured the availability of the participants and asked their permission to be part of the research and informed them of the purpose of the study and supplemental awareness in my study.

Second, it was explained to the participants that any confidential information would be treated with utmost confidentiality. Interviews are structured according to an interview guide made by the researcher, which outlines themes to be covered during the interview. The interview guide is typically without specification of how to formulate exact questions, and questions will be open-ended to encourage the respondents to give long elaborated answers.

Third, the interview was audio recorded through a mobile phone. Everything that transpired during the interview was put into record.

Lastly, the audio recorded interview was transcribed word for word.

Data Analysis

From the transcribed data gathered, necessary steps were undertaken. Gathered data were summarized, transcribed, translated and analyzed. Data analysis in qualitative research is defined as the process of systematically searching and arranging the interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual materials that the researcher accumulates to increase the understanding of the phenomenon (Bogdan & Biklen, 1982).

The process of analyzing qualitative data predominantly involves coding or categorizing the data. Thus, this includes sorting out vast amount of raw information by following important patterns then drawing significance from the information and hence constructing a logical chain of evidence (Patton, 2002).

Moreover, data processing occurred during the period of transcription of the results. In this study, after transcribing the individual interviews, statements relating to the topic were categorized into fundamental concepts that reflect specific ideas. In the context of thematic analysis, the process of data analysis consisted of categorizing the data and analyzing it thoroughly. The responses of the participants were organized into main themes that reflect the many facets of the phenomenon.

A thematic analysis was conducted to validate that the analysis of the responses of the participant was appropriate.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher acknowledges the importance and sensitivity of conducting a qualitative multiple case study and therefore follows the ethical considerations of this study.

The participants were given consent form indicating their willingness to participate and to avoid violating some ethical issues. Informed consent is the most common tool in ensuring ethical acceptability (Emanuel, Wendler, & Grady ,2000). However, the purpose of informed consent is to make sure that the participant of the research were informed of the potential risks, benefits, and the alternatives to the research, with the understanding that they are participating in the research voluntarily and making their participation decision without coercion.

Ethics are based on the researcher's integrity and aim to define the qualities or virtues required for a researcher to conduct in morally

or ethically upright manners. Research subjects must not be exposed to any form of injury under any circumstances.

Aside from bracketing, the two primary ethical concepts that apply to research are beneficence and non-maleficence. These principles encompass the core precept of prioritizing the avoidance of damage. If participants decide to withdraw their consent at any point throughout the study, they have the freedom to do so. No one took any action, and all individuals persisted until the conclusion.

Results and Discussion

Research informants were chosen based on the uniqueness of their story as an English teachers who shifted careers. In-depth interview was done during the interview with the informants. All throughout the entire interview, adherence to the informants' confidentiality of their identity and credibility was observed. Their responses were transcribed and analyzed. Themes were drawn out from their responses which paint the picture of their experiences as an English teachers who shifted careers.

The presentation of the sequence for this chapter was determined by the order of the research questions in the interview guide. The discussions section emphasized the key themes, emerged from the questionnaire and supported with related literature and studies.

The key participants in this study are three English teachers of Davao De Oro bearing different teaching life-story. Significant stories and experiences are gathered and presented in this section. The study utilized structured themes and emerging themes as the basis for discussing the findings. Each correlated with relevant literature and studies to significantly enhance the discussion.

Reasons for Deciding to Teach English. This structured theme summarizes the views three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. The emerging themes are taking it as second option, and enhancement of pedagogy. These are the reasons of the informants for deciding to teach English.

We all have initial choices when it comes to our careers, but sometimes those choices do not turn out for us. The informants chose the course as their second option because they have chosen to enroll in it instead, they have chosen it to use English for different purposes could it be in the teaching, English as secondary language. Akbari (2015) stated that, in the twenty-first century, English is required subject in most countries where it is spoken as second language or foreign language thus people major in it.

Furthermore, English majors chose English for Enhancement of Pedagogy. This is essential to strengthen the enhancement of pedagogy and this would help English majors being capable in course and use what they learn in the future. To prepare them to be an English teachers they are involve in different activities such as reading, writing, speaking, debate and etc., Discussion and debate are usually co-curricular activities, (Othman, 2005; Othman et al., 2013). English majors also typically engage in research, language studies, and internships as integral components of their academic and professional development. The English teachers provides learners the chance to cultivate a diverse set of proficiency, such as analytical reasoning, effective expression, investigative aptitude, and ingenuity, that can equip them for a plethora of professional paths. It is necessary to acquire these for the enhancement of the pedagogy in English. Rockstroh (2013) It has been asserted that the teacher is the primary factor that affects student learning, and effective teaching usually stems from a highly skilled educator. Undoubtedly, certain teachers possess a natural talent for aiding students in their learning journey. However, a profound understanding of the learning process, the growth of learners, and the academic materials are essential elements of good instruction (Roth and Swail, 2000).

Description of the Experiences in Teaching English. Worthwhile Experience is of the descriptions of the informants in their experiences in teaching English. Teaching English is a mission of every English teacher that should impart to be the vessel of educating the minds, Harris and Sass (2009) discovered a substantial correlation between teacher effectiveness and teacher personality traits, particularly empathy, intellect, subject matter expertise, and teaching abilities.

In addition, teaching English is also tricky and complicated, teaching and learning. English is broad teacher will also considered reading, literature, language and proficiency. According to Wolff (2003) English proficiency is considered a necessary qualification for individuals to compete in the global arena, rather than just a foreign language to be learned, the learning of the students should be balance in term of analyzation, comprehension, criticism and even literature.

One's Unforgettable Experiences in Teaching English. Informants share their unforgettable experiences in teaching English. The emerging themes gathered from this structured theme are: brainstorming teaching strategies, teaching broad literature topics, and student learning from the teacher.

Utilize active learning, technology integration, and differentiated instruction to engage students effectively, brainstorming teaching strategies to have productive learning outcomes that address the needs of the students, as one of the informants revealed that there are students who cannot read well and stress when it come to learning English, a teacher is always responsible for addressing the needs and English teachers can do that. According to Oman et al. (2008), many students experience ongoing stress to achieve high academic results. Various adaptive behaviors have been examined throughout the extensive research on stress, despite the controversial issue surrounding the concept of coping strategies (Stanislawski, 2019) meeting student needs, it is possible for English major graduates to be faced with the task of fulfilling the diverse needs of students, including students who have impairments or special needs, as well as students who originated from many cultural and linguistic origin..

Teaching literature is broad topic, it requires effort and time to study and discuss it, The review by Paran (2008) emphasizes the variety of English language study options that also include literature and foreign language instruction. Conducting research on teachers' experiences, in-service needs, and comprehension of critical conceptions is a crucial first step towards advancing the profession. According to Komulainen and Rajakaltio (2017), teachers play a crucial role as pedagogical leaders by imparting their pupils with literature-related ideas that carry significant moral or ideological implications. Further, with alternative philosophical frameworks concerning the nature of human existence, social structures, and the broader global context. This makes research into the teacher experience particularly important.

Another unforgettable experience considered by the informant in reminiscing the simple learning but it has a big impact for her as a teacher. Student learn from the teacher and vice versa, According to Rockstroh (2013), the teacher has the greatest impact on students' learning, and effective instruction usually results from having a highly competent teacher. According to Wolff (2003), knowing English is now seen as a prerequisite for people to compete on a worldwide scale, as opposed to merely being a foreign language that needs to be acquired. The efficiency of English language instruction and learning is reflected in the level of English competence among the Filipino populace.

Challenges Encountered During Practice Teaching Experience. This structured theme summarizes the views of three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers. The emerging themes are Time management, and catching students' interest.

One of the challenges encountered during practice teaching is the time management. The time for giving activities and assessing them can indeed be very challenging. Pay attention to the result instead than just keeping yourself busy. The way that one uses their time rather than how they manage it is more likely to affect their time management. Those with strong time management abilities will prioritize their tasks and focus their time and energy on the most important ones first. (Sandra Ika and others, 2013)

One of the challenging part also is catching students' interest, in catching interest the teaching should be fun and updated in trends, ask also what are the strategies other teachers used. They may have shaped a good view of the purpose of contemporary methods of instructions is to effectively convey acquired knowledge, innate qualities, developed skills, and past experiences to learners, specifically in the context of studying English. Experienced instructors want just to keep up with new advances alongside their students to enhance their abilities and contribute to the local community and national wealth. In order to effectively educate, the instructor must employ several instructional techniques to impart knowledge and mastery to the learners (Mustafa, 2014). Educating refers to range in activities undertaken by a teacher in a particular educational context to assist students in achieving specified educational and learning objectives, which are determined by the chosen teaching approach (Hamadnah & Obeidat, 2011). Additionally, experienced teachers possess a more comprehensive and diverse perspective on professional excellence. Their talents and teaching procedures mirror this, using current methods to enhance pupils' mental and intellectual capacities, particularly in English. Detected notable variations in the meta cognitive thinking abilities of English language instructors in Jordan, attributed to their level of teaching experience, favoring those with less experience (Al-Shra'a & Al-Eidi's 2019). Also, according to Al-Eidi's (2017) study contradicts this claim, as it revealed no significant alterations in English language teaching methodologies.

Challenges Encountered in Teaching English Subjects. This structured theme summarizes the views three English teacher as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are in making students understand the lesson, comprehension level and explaining in jargons.

One of the informants revealed that teaching English subject is not difficult but what makes it challenging is that how teachers deliver to the students in easier way. Teaching necessitates commitment, loyalty, and goes beyond simply acquiring a set of teaching techniques or imitating the behavior of another educator, even if they are very skilled. as cited in Roth and Swain (2000). Use modern strategies that it is easy to remember for the students and strategies that are fun and make it easier for them.

Unpacking competencies while hitting the comprehension level of the students, since the students are diverse in terms of skills, capabilities and even comprehension, this is the common challenge that the informant seen in the education, environment and self confidence also a factor that help develop the comprehension level of the learners. (Nakhalah, 2016). The research has encompassed various subjects, including the educational setting, societal surroundings, and familial environment. The study found that the most common challenges encountered by students when studying English include include anxiety of committing errors, introversion, and a deficiency in self-assurance. These are the typical obstacles that students studying in English must overcome.

The experience of the informants in explaining jargons words this may sometimes hinders the understanding of the message when communicating. Meanwhile English-language subject teachers are more likely to have an easier time adapting because they are familiar with more comprehensible terms. However, both individuals had challenges, particularly when they began working as teachers outside of their profession. This situation demands additional time and effort to acquire knowledge in a different subject (Melloria et al., 2023).

Ways these Challenges Affect Oneself and One's Career Choice.

This structured theme summarizes the views three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are felt like starting from scratch, lost willingness to teach, and difficulty in managing several students.

Shifting career felt like starting from scratch, it takes time to adjust the current career which really affect the career choice of the informants. According to Carless & Arnup (2011), a career shift can also involve changing jobs within a different industry or category and obtaining new training that renders prior experience and responsibilities essentially obsolete.

Challenges can be a reasons also of losing Willingness to teach, due to various challenges informants lost the eagerness to continue the teaching career. In addition applying or getting a teaching job is difficult because sometimes your competitors are also good in speaking the language. Feng and Chen (2016) pointed out that English major graduates may encountered difficulties in finding employment and have no particular benefits on the labor market because the total number of individuals proficient in spoken English is increasing due to globalization. Maintaining teachers' willingness to educate is largely dependent on professional development (Desimone, 2009). Enhancing instructional practices and work satisfaction requires continual learning opportunities and training (Guskey, 2002).

Overseeing several students can be difficult because of their varying demands, behaviors, and the task of monitoring their development. Striking a balance between providing individualized attention and managing the classroom can be challenging, particularly when taking into account factors such as class size, available resources, and time limitations. Strategies such as individualized instruction and creating good classroom settings are effective, but the ability to being adaptable is essential for making adjustments to the dynamics of students. One significant challenge encountered by educators is addressing the varied learning requirements of pupils within a unified classroom setting. Research has emphasized the significance of incorporating varied education methodologies to accommodate a wide range of learning preferences, talents, and area of interests (Tomlinson, 2014). Through the implementation of tailored educational experiences, educators can more effectively address the unique requirements of their students and foster academic advancement (Hall, Strangman, & Meyer, 2003).

Reasons in shifting careers from Teaching English. This structured theme summarizes the views three English Majors as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are Health Condition , Salary Wise, and To Have a Stable Job.

The choice to transition away from teaching as a result of health concerns can be impacted by a range of factors pertaining to both physical and emotional well-being. Studies indicate that educators may encounter health obstacles that can hinder their capacity to carry out their teaching responsibilities proficiently. It is also important to have a work-life balance, professional-life balance refers to the comprehensive integration of professional and personal life domains, as defined by Greenhaus and Allen (2011). The research in this field aims to establish a clear definition and conceptual understanding of work-life balance, as well as investigate its subjective perceptions and meanings among various groups. The lack of balance between work and personal life can lead to negative effects on individuals' physical and mental health, overall well-being, and their ability to perform well in their jobs (Shockley et al., 2017). The research investigates the effects of work-life conflict, extended work hours, and workplace stress on many outcomes, including burnout, turnover intentions, and work-family strain.

In addition, In practicality, in pursuing career and a job it is also important to choose salary wise, that it can compensate your hard work and provide your daily needs in life. Economic factors, including salary considerations, also play a significant role in educators' decisions to transition away from English teaching (Clark & Garcia, 2016). Teaching salaries may not always align with the cost of living or with salaries offered in other industries, leading educators to explore alternative career paths. Changes in educational policies and reform initiatives can also influence the attractiveness of teaching careers (Robinson, 2015). Salary is a frequent factor in turnover among EL instructors with six to ten years of experience and more, as having financial worries may make teaching less engaging for them. Another factor contributing to the desire to quit for EL instructors with more years of experience in the classroom is the working environment, which may severely impact the harmony between work and personal life and lessen interactions with students. Teaching necessitates commitment, loyalty, and goes beyond simply acquiring a set of teaching techniques or imitating the behavior of another educator, even if they are very skilled as cited in Roth and Swain (2000).

In the current educational environment, a significant number of educators place a higher value on job stability and security than they do on pursuing occupations that are closely related to their academic majors. The purpose of this review is to gain an understanding of the variables that are driving this preference, provide an analysis of the impact that it has on education, and provide potential solutions to ensure that teacher-student alignment is effective inside schools.

Description of the Difference of One's Life with Current Career and the Teaching English Experience. This structured theme summarizes the views of three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are no difference at all, light workload, and different work regulations.

The informant was of the opinion that there is no distinction between teaching English and shifting career. Acquiring knowledge of the English language provides individuals the opportunity to explore a wide range of literature, art, music, and movies from various cultural backgrounds (Crystal, 2003). It allows individuals to interact with worldwide viewpoints and promote intercultural comprehension. English serves as the universal language of the tourism sector, enabling effective communication between tourists and service providers around the globe (Graddol, 2006).

On the other hand, the participant believed that there is no difference at al since his current career is somehow connected to education. English instruction prioritizes language acquisition, literacy development, and communication skills. However, non-English topics also

have a role in enhancing students' language competency through content-based language learning (Wright & Elgar, 2010). Incorporating activities and conversations that use language into the training of subjects other than English enhances the development of academic language and fosters linkages across different areas of study (Cummins, 2000). Both English and non-English disciplines foster the development of critical thinking skills, analytical reasoning, and problem-solving ability in pupils (Hattie & Timperley, 2007). Although English and non-English disciplines may have distinct content and language emphasis, there is a significant convergence in teaching methodologies, instructional approaches, and student achievements. Teachers can utilize fundamental teaching principles, such as focusing on the needs of individual students, tailoring instruction to different learning styles, and fostering the growth of critical thinking skills, to improve their efficacy in teaching various subjects. By acknowledging the parallels between teaching English and disciplines other than English, educators can embrace interdisciplinary methodologies that foster comprehensive learning and address the varied requirements of students. From what the participants learned from both English and non-English, it was applied to the current career and help him to become more productive and excellent in his current career.

Comparing workload between teaching and non-teaching career has a big difference. Factors such as heavy workloads, demanding schedules, and administrative burdens contribute to dissatisfaction among English teachers (Brown, 2017). Economic factors, including salary considerations, also play a significant role in educators' decisions to transition away from English teaching (Clark & Garcia, 2016). Given the fact that teaching necessitates commitment, loyalty, and goes beyond simply acquiring a set of teaching techniques or imitating the behavior of another educator, even if they are very skilled. as cited in Roth and Swain (2000) teacher self-efficacy, which compound the stressful overload of classroom responsibilities that causes teacher resignations Klassen & Chiu (2010) compared to other career teaching is much heavy and other job is lighter as the informant stated that being with his career now is much better compared to teaching.

In modern society, different occupations adhere to specific regulations that dictate their work habits. Fire officers and teachers are two crucial industries that have distinct roles and regulatory systems. Comparing to the work regulation of fire officer and a teacher has a big difference The primary goal of fire officers' work in a highly regulated, controlled setting is to ensure public safety during emergencies Health and Safety Standards, To reduce the risks involved with fighting fires, firefighters are required to follow strict health and safety guidelines.

According to Smith, (2018) This involves adhering to National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) rules and Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) guidelines. Training and Certification Requirements, In order to obtain the credentials they need, such as Emergency Medical Technician (EMT) and Firefighter I and II, fire officers must complete demanding training programs. According to Jones and Brown (2020), it is imperative to undergo ongoing training in order to preserve expertise and stay current with emerging methods and tools. operating Procedures, To regulate different facets of fighting fires, conducting rescue missions, and handling hazardous chemicals, fire departments create particular operating procedures. According to Johnson et al. (2019), these protocols guarantee synchronized reactions and efficient handling of emergency circumstances. Teachers work in an industry that is regulated by a unique set of laws designed to support the education and welfare of students. Important guidelines for educators consist of: Curriculum Standards which Teachers are required to follow curriculum standards set forth by the state, which specify the knowledge and abilities that students should learn at each grade level. Practices for instructional design and assessment are guided by these criteria (Adams, 2017). Requirements for Professional Development: In order to improve their instruction and stay up to date with new approaches and trends in education, teachers are frequently obliged to participate in continuing professional development activities. For the purpose of renewing a teacher license, many states require a specific amount of hours of professional development (Brown & Miller, 2021). Guidelines for Student Assessment, Teachers are in charge of evaluating students' learning using a variety of techniques, including as project-based assessments, classroom evaluations, and standardized examinations. They have to adhere to the rules for impartial and just evaluation procedures, Garcia, et al. (2018).

Insights Gained from Teaching English. This structured theme summarizes the views three English Majors as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are importance of relating the subject to learners, nice experience with students showing interest, and English a Very Powerful language.

According to Ambrose et al. (2010), relating the subject matter to learners enhances engagement and promotes deeper understanding. Additionally, Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of connecting the material to students' experiences and interests to make learning meaningful. It is essential to always integrate relevant lesson that the students can use also to their future career choice. Relating the subject matter to learners is essential for effective teaching and learning (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). By connecting the material to students' interests, experiences, and prior knowledge, educators enhance engagement, promote deeper understanding, personalize learning, and highlight the relevance of the material to students' lives.

Versatility, To think outside the box, you need to be adaptable and versatile in your approach to problem-solving (Girotra & Netessine, 2013). This means being open to exploring unconventional ideas, perspectives, and solutions that may not conform to traditional norms or methods. A versatile thinker is willing to challenge assumptions, experiment with different approaches, and embrace ambiguity and uncertainty.

Teaching becomes more effective with experience, as educators develop a repertoire of teaching techniques, classroom management strategies, and ways to engage students (Hattie, 2009). Experienced teachers are able to anticipate challenges, adapt their teaching to meet students' needs, and facilitate meaningful learning experiences.

Educators find it highly satisfying when students demonstrate real enthusiasm in learning. When students exhibit inquisitiveness, involvement, and eagerness for acquiring knowledge, it generates a tangible vitality within the classroom (Ryan & Deci, 2000). As an instructor, it is highly rewarding to observe the glimmer of curiosity in their eyes and experience their enthusiastic engagement in talks, projects, and activities. Observing the process of knowledge acquisition and growth in receptive minds is like to witnessing the germination and flourishing of seeds. This experience serves as a powerful reminder of the transformative influence that education can exert on the development of young individuals. Student engagement and interest have a strong correlation with academic achievement and accomplishment (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004). Students that demonstrate a strong enthusiasm for their studies are more inclined to establish ambitious objectives, persevere in the face of difficulties, and attain favorable results academically and in other areas. Observing pupils who genuinely display interest in learning is a profound encounter that ignites enthusiasm, stimulates development, and cultivates an environment of inquisitiveness and continuous learning (Ryan & Deci, 2000). As educators, it is crucial for us to foster and develop students' enthusiasm for learning, as this is not only highly gratifying but also necessary for enabling them to achieve their maximum capabilities and succeed in a constantly evolving society.

Insights after Going through all Experiences. This structured theme summarizes the views of three English Majors as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are Teaching the Noblest Profession, Finding it Necessary for Further Education, and Established Understanding with others.

Teaching is indeed a noblest profession where it is a profession where one must continually learn and grow. Everything can be learned, and educators embrace ongoing professional development to stay current and effective in their practice (Smith, 2018). According to Dweck (2006), the belief that everything can be learned is rooted in the growth mindset theory, which posits that individuals can develop their abilities through effort and persistence. This This viewpoint highlights the significance of establishing a mindset focused on learning and embracing adversities as chances for personal development. Teaching is not just teaching the subject matter but it is more than that, teaching teaches us to be more flexible, creative, versatile and it help us develop of who and what we are right now, that whenever you are in industry teachers always excel in doing the chosen career.

To ensure excellent instruction and promote student achievement, educators must pursue further education to obtain a deeper understanding of their subject, pedagogy, and student requirements (Johnson, 2020). Effective educators are flexible and open-minded, adapting their teaching methods to satisfy the different needs of their students and embracing new ideas and approaches (Jones, 2016). Pursuing graduate school is essential because it will help you to level up your education and professional and personal growth. Even if you pursue another master's in graduate school, it is still necessary because it does not mean that after graduating from college, the learning should stop but as we all know that education is a continuous process.

Building strong relationships and establishing understanding with students, colleagues, and the community is paramount. Effective communication, empathy, and collaboration are essential for creating a supportive learning environment and promoting positive outcomes for all (Brown & Miller, 2017). By building strong relationships with others, we will also understand them in terms of the use of the language, their culture and traditions, and also their emotional capacity, in building connection you should always choose the right communication. Teaching is indeed a noble profession that requires continuous learning, a commitment to further education, and the establishment of understanding with others.

Plans With One's Career as an English Teacher. This structured theme summarizes the views of three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses, two themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are To be Part-time Teacher, and Do not Have Plan Yet.

They say A teacher is always a teacher, and two of the informants are still willing to teach the English language, however, not as a full-time teacher but as part-time only. Draw upon the past teaching experience to identify their strengths, areas for growth, and teaching preferences. Reflect on what aspects of teaching you enjoyed most and how you can leverage these in a part-time role (Marzano & Pickering, 2017). Still it continue making a positive impact in the lives of the student while enjoying the benefits of flexibility and work-life balance.

Other informant do not have plan yet in his English teaching career because he believed that he need to develop more on his knowledge and teaching career, however he believed that he will continue getting the masters degree but not connected in English teaching. According to Perna et al., 2014 Reflect on your career aspirations and personal interests to determine how graduate education aligns with your goals, Explore different graduate programs related to your field of interest, considering factors such as program reputation, faculty expertise, and curriculum content

Suggestions to People who Wish to be an English Teacher. This structured theme summarizes the views of three English teachers as for their reasons for shifting careers from English teaching. Out of their responses three themes were drawn out. The emerging themes are to try to be excellent, to be confident in teaching, and not to be pressured.

English teachers always excel in many ways. To be excellent, according to Tomlinson (2014). Tailor your teaching methods to accommodate diverse learning styles, abilities, and backgrounds of students. Use a variety of instructional strategies, such as visual aids, hands-on activities, and cooperative learning, to engage learners effectively. Encourage students to analyze, evaluate, and interpret texts critically. Provide opportunities for discussion, debate, and reflection to deepen their understanding of literary themes, characters, and techniques (Fisher & Frey, 2014) also, engage in regular self-reflection and assessment of your teaching practices to identify areas of strength and areas for growth. Seek feedback from students, colleagues, and mentors to continuously improve your instructional effectiveness (Danielson, 2013)

In addition, to be confident, Be kind to yourself and recognize that setbacks and failures are part of the learning process. Cultivate self-compassion by treating yourself with understanding and forgiveness (Neff, 2003). Let your passion drive your determination to overcome obstacles and achieve your long-term aspirations (Duckworth, 2016). Inspire others with your passion and enthusiasm. Be a positive influence on your colleagues and peers by bringing energy, creativity, and optimism to your interactions and collaborations (Fredrickson, 2001).

Avoid feeling pressured in professional or personal pursuits, it is essential to develop strategies for managing stress, setting realistic expectations, and maintaining a healthy work-life balance. Be kind and compassionate towards yourself, especially during challenging times. Acknowledge your efforts and accomplishments, and treat yourself with the same kindness and understanding you would offer to a friend (Neff, 2003). Divert your focus from aiming perfection to making a progress and learning from mistakes. Embrace a growth mindset that values effort, resilience, and continuous improvement (Dweck, 2006).

Conclusion

Based on the data I have gathered, different experiences of English teachers shifting careers were explored and unfolded. They have shared their struggles, inspirations, reasons, insights, and plans. As a researcher, I could explore the untold stories and experiences of the participants. I was moved as I got to see the determination and how they overcame their challenging experiences. There are many adversities as they face the demands of life.

I believe that the challenges they encountered make them strong, and they decide to choose which career path they should consider, whether they would continue teaching English in the future or totally shift careers from English teaching as long as they are happy with their chosen careers.

While your approach to English teaching may diverge from traditional methods, your unwavering dedication to learning and your persistent determination to positively impact others remain steadfast. By embracing the opportunities presented to you, the profound effect of your work as an English teacher will endure, even as you embark on new professional journeys.

English education serves as more than a pathway to linguistic proficiency; it serves as a gateway to developing critical thinking skills and fostering a global perspective among students. Educators establish a dynamic educational setting in which students acquire proficiency in English language alongside developing skills in critical analysis, evaluation, and synthesis of information. This empowers them to navigate complexities in both academic and real-world contexts, preparing them to contribute meaningfully to a rapidly changing global society.

In general, it is important to remember that teaching is not limited to one classroom or the contents of textbooks, rather it goes beyond physical limitations. Your influence extends far beyond the subjects you teach; you are molding the intellect and emotions of people you come across throughout your journey. As you move through your career, continue to embody the qualities of curiosity, empathy, and passion that truly characterize the essence of teaching. Your career path serves as evidence of the significant effect that education can have, and everyone worldwide eagerly anticipates the valuable contributions you will make in your future endeavors.

The following implications are considered for future researchers:

First, the study suggests further research be conducted to substantiate these responses using greater number of participants. The greater the number of participants the more life stories will be explored and unfolded.

Second, as a researcher, I suggest to include other municipalities or provinces as part of your research locale. This will allow investigating and exploring more stories about the phenomenon.

Third, the study conducted in a Davao de Oro but in limited municipalities, further research could be done to the entire municipalities of Davao De Oro.

Lastly, another research could be conducted to discover more stories from English teachers shifting careers.

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